

OuterMotion Beyond01: Calibration-Free Full-Body Pose Reconstruction in the Wild via Foot-Mounted Wide-Angle Cameras

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Abstract—Untethered full-body motion capture of natural human movement in uncontrolled environments remains an open problem. Marker-based optical motion capture systems require purpose-built spaces and expert operators; inertial motion capture suits require numerous wearable sensors, involve calibration in each setup session and are susceptible to magnetic drift; and markerless video systems largely reduce the complexity of the motion capture process, yet they still depend on fixed, calibrated capture volumes that constrain where recordings can take place. We present a calibration-free system built around two wide-angle cameras clipped to the laces of ordinary shoes. Oriented upward from ground level, the foot-mounted cameras provide a persistent egocentric view of the body throughout the gait cycle without requiring any additional wearable hardware. A transformer-based deep learning architecture reconstructs full body skeletal pose directly from the dual foot camera streams without any calibration. Evaluated during outdoor walking and running against OpenCap-derived biomechanical reference data from 23 participants, the system achieves an overall PA-MPJPE of 41.5 mm, with hip and knee flexion/extension RMSE of 8.5° and 8.1° respectively. At under 35 g per sensor, 2 hours battery life, local storage sufficient for 8 hour recordings, and with data uploaded automatically for cloud-side inference, the system requires no specialist operator, imposes minimal burden on the wearer, and can be deployed freely in home and outdoor environments, enabling long-term and natural biomechanical data collection at a scale that current motion capture systems cannot match.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human motion analysis often depends on specialised infrastructure. Optical motion capture, the current gold standard, delivers sub-millimetre marker position [1] by tracking reflective markers under a fixed array of calibrated cameras. It requires expert operators, purpose-built spaces, and time-intensive marker placement [2], making it impractical for field studies, longitudinal monitoring, or any setting outside a dedicated facility [3].

Inertial motion capture (IMC) systems are not spatially constrained, relying instead on a large number of wearable sensors (up to 17) [4], imposing operational overheads in sensor placement and by requiring calibration procedures lasting several minutes [5]. Variability in sensor placement between repeated setup sessions is a well-documented source of systematic error that is only partially mitigated by calibration procedures [6]. Beyond placement variability, magnetometer-

based heading estimates are susceptible to corruption by ferrous or magnetic influences [7], causing global orientation to drift unpredictably in real-world environments.

Deep-learning video-based systems remove the need for wearable hardware entirely and have achieved accuracy suitable for multiple applications in controlled settings [8], [9], [10]. However, this advantage does not necessarily remove the typical 4×6 m capture volume constraint, because external multi-camera systems still depend on the region covered by the calibrated cameras [8], [10]. In multi-camera markerless systems, calibration of the camera setup is typically required [9]. Variable illumination, motion blur during faster activities, scene clutter and training domain limitations present additional challenges in outdoor environments [11]. Removing the capture volume constraint entirely requires moving the camera off the fixed infrastructure and onto the subject itself [12], [13].

Egocentric video-based pose estimation mounts one or more cameras directly on the body, allowing the camera system to move with the user rather than requiring a fixed external capture volume [12]. This approach allows for truly untethered pose estimation with no external infrastructure and no restriction on the recording location. However, the egocentric viewpoint introduces substantial pose estimation challenges, including self-occlusion, perspective distortion, limited field of view (FOV) coverage, and lower accuracy compared to those seen in fixed-camera video approaches [13]. Egocentric setups are often mounted on the head, which makes lower limb reconstruction challenging, as the lower body is more frequently occluded by the torso, arms, or clothing, which can reduce the reliability of lower body joint angle estimates [12].

To target lower limb kinematics directly, we proposed a pair of wide-angle upward-facing cameras; one camera per shoe; with both streams processed jointly by a deep neural network. Three design choices motivated the foot-mounted configuration. Positioning the cameras at ground level and directing them upward kept the entire body in frame throughout all phases of the gait cycle. The lace-mounted sensor also maintained a stable, repeatable geometric relationship to the foot skeleton, and inter-session placement variability was low. Finally, the architecture required no calibration sequence; users clipped on the sensors and began recording immediately.

Fig. 1: **Comparison of full-body motion capture systems across usage environment, operator accessibility, and data scalability.** Traditional marker-based and full-body IMU motion capture systems provide high-quality motion data, but they are typically limited to laboratory or supervised environments and require expert operation. Portable markerless systems, including multi-camera and single-smartphone approaches, reduce setup constraints and can support clinic or home-based recording, but still depend on capture volume and operator availability. In contrast, a foot mounted camera system can be distributed to users for repeated recordings during their regular sport sessions, enabling motion capture in natural conditions without operator involvement.

Each shoe unit additionally incorporated a 6-axis inertial measurement unit (IMU). IMU data was recorded synchronously with the camera frames but was not yet connected to the inference pipeline; integration was planned as a future extension to provide explicit foot-contact anchoring and global orientation estimation.

Each shoe was instrumented with one 35 g sensor, resulting in an equivalent added mass per shoe. Even for the most weight sensitive sports, such as running, reported masses for footwear in the literature range from approximately 175 to 415 g per shoe, based on racing shoe masses in trained runners [14], [15]. The added sensor mass is therefore small relative to the reported range of running shoe masses and is expected to have only a limited effect on the movement form, particularly given that footwear below approximately 440 g per pair has been reported not to impair running economy [16].

Together, these properties represent a practical shift in the conditions under which biomechanical data can be collected. The system was ready to use within tens of seconds, imposed no perceivable burden on the wearer, and could be operated without specialist training. Recordings were not confined to a laboratory or clinic; users could move freely outdoors. Data

was uploaded to a cloud server where it was processed. This removed the specialist operator from the data collection loop entirely, making it practical to gather biomechanical data across diverse populations, environments, and activities at a scale that current motion capture systems could not match.

This design enables large-scale data collection for applications that are currently impractical with laboratory-based systems: rehabilitation programmes requiring movement monitoring over weeks or months outside the clinic; sports performance tracking across training sessions in natural environments; occupational health assessments conducted at the workplace rather than under controlled conditions; and longitudinal studies that need repeated measurements from large cohorts.

II. SYSTEM DESIGN

Each shoe was fitted with one sensor unit clipped onto the lace area at the dorsal mid-foot position as illustrated in Figure 2b. Each sensor had a wide-angle camera and a 6-axis IMU comprising a 3-axis accelerometer and a 3-axis gyroscope and weighed under 35 g; all recorded data was stored locally on the device.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 2: (a) Participant equipped with OuterMotion Beyond01 sensor units during outdoor running. (b) Close-up of the sensor unit clipped to the lace area at the dorsal mid-foot position. No additional wearable hardware is required.

No additional wearable hardware was required. The sensor was capable of continuous recording for up to two hours per charge.

Before each recording session, both units were connected via USB-C to synchronise their internal clocks to a common reference, enabling temporal alignment between the two camera streams. Data offload was automatic: when the sensors were charging within range of a Wi-Fi network, recorded files were transferred to the processing server without any manual intervention. Upload took approximately two to three times the recording duration depending on signal quality. Pose estimation ran server-side after upload; on a laptop equipped with an Intel Core i9-13900HK and an NVIDIA RTX 4070 Laptop GPU,

Fig. 3: Synchronised wide-angle views from the left (left panel) and right (right panel) foot-mounted cameras during outdoor running. The fisheye perspective from foot level keeps the full body in frame throughout the gait cycle.

processing completes in approximately 2.5 times the recording duration.

The IMU was sampled and its data was stored alongside the camera frames, but it was not connected to the ML inference pipeline. Integration was planned as a future extension to provide explicit foot-contact event detection and global orientation estimation.

Each unit was equipped with a fisheye lens, mounted to point upward and toward the medial side of the body. This orientation provided a persistent egocentric view of the full body from ground level throughout all phases of a normal gait cycle. A sample of paired frames from left and right sides are presented in Figure 3

Each camera captured frames at 30 Hz. All data modalities were timestamped to within 2 ms across sensors, ensuring accurate temporal alignment.

III. ML-BASED POSE RECONSTRUCTION

The pose estimation pipeline followed the sequential deep learning architecture illustrated in Figure 4. Synchronized image frames from the left and right foot-mounted cameras were passed jointly through a deep neural network, which produced per-camera 2D joint-keypoint heatmaps. A pose decoder then lifted these heatmaps into a 3D skeletal representation. The resulting 3D keypoint positions were used in OpenSim [17] to scale the musculoskeletal model and subsequently solve inverse kinematics (IK), thereby recovering anatomical joint angles from the predicted keypoint positions. Both the 2D heatmap-estimation and 3D pose estimation modules were implemented as transformer-based deep neural networks. Sharing additional architectural details will be considered in future manuscripts.

The Visual Encoder produced per-camera 2D probability heatmaps localising each joint center in the image plane, each accompanied by a per-keypoint confidence score. These heatmaps were passed to the Pose Decoder, which lifted them into a full body 3D pose defined as 18 joint center positions in a pelvis-centered coordinate frame, also accompanied by per-joint confidence scores.

The predicted keypoint set comprised 18 anatomical landmarks spanning the full body. For the lower limbs, these included the pelvis, bilateral hips, knees, ankles, and the first and fifth metatarsophalangeal landmarks (MTP1 and

MTP5). The MTP1 and MTP5 landmarks provide medial and lateral forefoot references, enabling the estimation of inversion–eversion motion. The spine was represented by the T9/T8 landmark, while the upper limbs were represented by bilateral shoulders, elbows, and wrists. The keypoint layout is shown in Figure 5.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

A. Participants

Twenty-three participants took part in the study (19 male, 4 female). Participants ranged in age from 21 to 39 years (23 ± 4.9 years), in height from 1.54 to 1.95 m (1.74 ± 0.10 m), and in body mass from 53 to 94 kg (72 ± 10.7 kg). Inclusion required participants to be aged 18 or over and free from any musculoskeletal condition that would alter their natural gait.

B. Data Collection and Processing

Data were collected during four outdoor activities performed at two locations: a running track and a brick-paved path with a vegetation background. All sessions took place during the daytime in sunny, partially cloudy, and overcast conditions, with no minimum illuminance threshold. The activity set comprised slow walking, brisk walking, slow running, and fast running. For each activity, participants were instructed to move at a self-selected pace corresponding to the requested activity level.

In total, 106 trials were recorded: 23 slow walking trials, 29 brisk walking trials, 28 slow running trials, 26 fast running trials.

Each trial was recorded within the OpenCap [10] capture volume using a three camera setup as illustrated in Figure 6. OpenCap served as the reference data system. Participants moved along a 4 m corridor towards and away from the cameras while maintaining a face-on orientation relative to the camera setup for a total of 60 seconds.

The recorded videos were processed offline using the OpenCap pipeline to estimate full body 3D joint center positions. These OpenCap-derived positions served as the reference data for model evaluation.

The left and right shoe sensors shared a common timestamp reference, enabling direct temporal alignment between both feet. To align the shoe sensor image streams with the OpenCap outputs, correlation-based synchronisation was performed between the two-dimensional keypoint trajectories extracted from the foot-sensor images and the OpenCap three-dimensional keypoint trajectories projected into the camera plane. For this process, the camera was assumed to be rigidly fixed to the foot segment.

Trials with incomplete or poor OpenCap reconstruction were excluded from the dataset, resulting in the final trial counts reported above. No additional data-exclusion criteria were applied.

C. Training

The dataset was divided into training, validation, and test sets using an 80–10–10 split. Splitting was performed at the

participant level, therefore, all trials from a given participant were assigned to only one split. This ensured that the validation and test sets contained participants who were never seen by the model during training. Unless stated otherwise, the results reported in this work are computed over the test set.

D. Evaluation Metrics

Model performance was evaluated using both 3D keypoint accuracy and joint angle accuracy. 3D pose accuracy was quantified using Procrustes-aligned mean per-joint position error (PA-MPJPE). PA-MPJPE was computed per frame; the median across all frames is reported throughout. PA-MPJPE was used because the present study focused on the accuracy of the estimated human pose rather than global position and orientation within the capture volume. This was particularly relevant for egocentric pose estimation, where the primary objective was to recover biomechanically meaningful joint motion rather than absolute body translation in the world coordinate system.

Joint angle accuracy was evaluated using the root mean square error (RMSE) between predicted and OpenCap-derived joint angles. The analysis was performed per segmented gait cycle. Gait cycles were identified using the Zeni method [18], which detects heel-strike and toe-off events from the displacement of foot-mounted markers relative to the pelvis. For each identified gait cycle, predicted and OpenCap joint angle trajectories were temporally aligned and compared over the cycle duration. RMSE and Pearson correlation coefficient, r , were then computed between the predicted and OpenCap joint angles within each cycle, and the median across all cycles and trials is reported.

In addition to median error metrics, catastrophic prediction failures were quantified at the frame level. A frame was considered catastrophic if any lower limb keypoint exceeded 100 mm PA-MPJPE (approximately $2 \times$ the median lower limb error). Catastrophic failures were reported as the percentage of frames meeting this criterion, broken down by activity level.

V. RESULTS

A. Keypoint Localization Accuracy

The model achieved an overall median PA-MPJPE of 41.5 mm across all 18 joints and 19 trials of the test set (Table I, Figure 8). For simplicity, only selected individual keypoints are reported. Errors increased monotonically with activity intensity (Figure 7): 37.4 mm for walking, 39.4 mm for brisk walking, 41.9 mm for slow running, and 52.4 mm for fast running.

Errors increased progressively toward distal joint centers from the origin (pelvis). Pelvis and hip errors were lowest (22.9 mm and 24.9 mm, respectively), followed by the knee (42.4 mm), ankle (46.3 mm), and the MTP keypoints (46.6 mm and 50.7 mm). The activity level relationship with error was most pronounced at distal joints: right-knee error rose from 37.3 mm during walking to 54.3 mm during fast running, whereas pelvis and hip errors were less affected across activities.

Fig. 4: Inference pipeline. Camera frames (green) feed a Visual Encoder, which produces per-camera 2D heatmaps with per-keypoint confidence scores. These feed a Pose Decoder that outputs a full body 3D pose and per-joint confidence scores. The 3D pose is passed to an IK solver (OpenSim) to recover joint angles. IMU fusion (dashed) is recorded but not yet active.

Upper limb accuracy was substantially lower, with the gap widening toward distal segments. Shoulder error (33.4 mm) was moderately higher than hip error (24.9 mm), elbow error (45.8 mm) slightly exceeded knee error (42.4 mm), and wrist error (68.5 mm) was significantly higher than MTP keypoint errors (46.6 mm).

B. Joint Angle Accuracy

Overall joint angle accuracy followed a proximal to distal increasing error pattern (Table II, Figure 9). Hip and knee flexion/extension achieved the lowest errors (8.5° , $r = 0.90$; and 8.1° , $r = 0.93$). Ankle flexion/extension showed high RMSE errors (10.4° , $r = 0.66$). Errors for shoulder flexion/extension are higher than hip and knee flexion/extension (10.3° , $r = 0.86$), while elbow flexion/extension errors are higher than the ankle (14.8° , $r = 0.56$).

Hip flexion/extension error had little variation across activity speeds, with per-activity RMSE ranging from 8.1° during fast running to 9.1° at brisk walking. Pearson r was 0.87 even at fast running, confirming that waveform shape match was preserved across the full speed range. Hip abduction/adduction yielded lower absolute RMSE (3.6°) but with reduced temporal correlation ($r = 0.66$). Hip rotation had a higher overall RMSE (7.9°) and the lowest temporal correlation among the hip planes ($r = 0.46$).

Knee flexion/extension achieved comparable overall accuracy to the hip ($r = 0.93$). Per-activity RMSE did not follow a monotonic speed trend, ranging from 7.3° at brisk walking to 8.7° at slow running, with $r \geq 0.91$ maintained across all activities.

Ankle flexion/extension had an overall RMSE of 10.4° ($r = 0.66$), higher than the knee. RMSE was highest during slow running (17.4°) and lowest at walking (8.4°), with temporal correlation r between 0.57 and 0.72 across activities.

Upper limb angles exhibited higher errors and lower temporal correlations than the proximal lower limb joints. Shoulder flexion/extension RMSE ranged from 7.9° during walking to 12.4° at slow running, while r remained high ($r = 0.86$ overall). Shoulder abduction/adduction presented lower absolute RMSE (5.6°) but also lower temporal correlation ($r = 0.32$).

Elbow flexion/extension had an overall RMSE of 14.8° and the lowest temporal correlation among the evaluated joints ($r = 0.56$). Correlation was $r = 0.76$ during brisk walking, but declined at higher speeds ($r = 0.39$ at slow running; $r = 0.42$ at fast running), suggesting increased prediction variability as arm swing becomes more pronounced.

C. Pose Visualisation

Figure 10 shows qualitative pose reconstruction results for representative frames from one trial. Each row displays a third-person view of the movement alongside the left and right foot camera images with predicted joint heatmaps, and a 3D keypoint overlay comparing both systems. The foot-mounted cameras maintained the body in view throughout the trial. Heatmaps show well-localised 2D keypoint predictions across limb segments; the 3D overlay reveals close agreement at proximal joints and larger deviations at distal extremities, consistent with the quantitative results in Table II.

D. Catastrophic failure rate

A total of **15.8%** of frames contained at least one lower limb joint keypoint exceeding 100 mm PA-MPJPE, with the proportion rising from **12.0%** during normal walking to **28.3%** at fast running.

VI. DISCUSSION

We presented a shoe-mounted dual camera system for full body pose reconstruction during outdoor locomotion. By relying solely on wide-angle images from two foot cameras, the system targeted a gap between stationary markerless capture and wearable inertial suits, such that it is untethered and operable without expert setup.

The system achieved an overall PA-MPJPE of 41.5 mm and hip, knee, and ankle flexion/extension RMSE of 8.5° , 8.1° , and 10.4° , respectively. Accuracy showed a proximal to distal gradient: proximal joint errors (pelvis, hip, shoulder) stayed within 23 to 33 mm, while ankle, elbow, and wrist errors reached 46 mm, 46 mm, and 69 mm respectively. Joint-angle correlation followed the same gradient; hip and knee flexion/extension Pearson r (0.90 and 0.93) were substantially higher than elbow and ankle flexion/extension ($r = 0.56$

TABLE I: PA-MPJPE (mm) per joint broken down by activity (bilateral joints L/R averaged, proximal to distal ordering within each region).

Joint	Walk	Brisk walk	Slow run	Fast run	Overall
<i>Lower limb</i>					
Pelvis	23.5	24.2	24.1	19.6	22.9
Hip	25.2	26.2	27.0	21.6	24.9
Knee	37.4	41.9	41.9	52.5	42.4
Ankle	42.7	43.3	43.3	59.5	46.3
MTP1	45.2	46.0	47.1	65.5	50.7
MTP5	42.5	43.5	41.4	63.1	46.6
<i>Upper limb</i>					
Shoulder	32.6	33.3	35.1	33.4	33.4
Elbow	37.5	40.3	50.9	56.6	45.8
Wrist	61.6	70.8	74.8	66.0	68.5
Overall (18 joints)	37.4	39.4	41.9	52.4	41.5

TABLE II: Joint angle RMSE ($^{\circ}$) and Pearson r (bilateral joints L/R averaged) broken down by activity. Catastrophic failure rate: percentage of frames in which at least one lower-limb keypoint exceeds 100 mm PA-MPJPE.

Joint / Plane	RMSE ($^{\circ}$)				
	Walk	Brisk walk	Slow run	Fast run	Overall
<i>Lower limb</i>					
Hip flex./ext.	8.4	9.1	8.3	8.1	8.5
Hip add./abd.	3.1	3.5	4.6	3.7	3.6
Hip rotation	6.9	8.8	9.0	6.8	7.9
Knee flex./ext.	8.5	7.3	8.7	8.3	8.1
Ankle flex./ext.	8.4	8.6	17.4	10.2	10.4
<i>Upper limb</i>					
Shoulder flex./ext.	7.9	9.2	12.4	11.8	10.3
Elbow flex./ext.	14.6	16.3	16.9	12.4	14.8
Joint / Plane	Pearson r				
	Walk	Brisk walk	Slow run	Fast run	Overall
<i>Lower limb</i>					
Hip flex./ext.	0.94	0.92	0.86	0.87	0.90
Hip add./abd.	0.68	0.70	0.62	0.65	0.66
Hip rotation	0.61	0.33	0.32	0.60	0.46
Knee flex./ext.	0.92	0.91	0.94	0.93	0.93
Ankle flex./ext.	0.70	0.72	0.57	0.67	0.66
<i>Upper limb</i>					
Shoulder flex./ext.	0.85	0.88	0.83	0.86	0.86
Elbow flex./ext.	0.71	0.76	0.39	0.42	0.56
Metric	Catastrophic failure rate (%)				
	Walk	Brisk walk	Slow run	Fast run	Overall
PA-MPJPE > 100 mm (lower limb)	12.0	13.0	14.1	28.3	15.8

and $r = 0.66$). Error increased monotonically with activity speed, rising 15 mm from walking to fast running, though the waveform shape of hip and knee kinematics was largely preserved ($r \geq 0.87$ even at fast running).

The high ankle angle RMSE relative to the hip and knee reflects two contributing factors. Because the foot segment is short, a given absolute keypoint deviation at the MTP landmarks produces a proportionally larger angular displacement after inverse kinematics than the same deviation would at the longer femur or tibia segments. Furthermore, a small deviation in the position of MTP1 and MTP5 in the modelled foot segment

propagate directly into the IK solution, introducing an angular offset in the computed ankle flexion/extension signal. The principled correction is to adjust the MTP keypoint locations within the OpenSim skeletal model such that the IK solution reproduces expected ankle kinematics. This adjustment can be derived from biomechanical knowledge of the activity; for instance, knowing that ankle flexion during level walking follows a characteristic range and waveform shape is sufficient to guide the correction. In an unsupervised pipeline, however, determining such priors is not trivial, as the expected kinematic characteristics must be inferred from the data itself.

Fig. 5: The 18 joint center keypoints predicted by the pose decoder: pelvis, bilateral hips, knees, ankles, 1st and 5th metatarsophalangeal joints (MTP1 and MTP5) for the lower limbs; T9/T8 for the spine; and bilateral shoulders, elbows, and wrists for the upper limbs.

The 3D pose was expressed in a pelvis-centered coordinate frame, meaning the pelvis is by definition at the origin and it should have zero positional error. Hip error was correspondingly low because the hips are rigidly coupled to the pelvis with a short lever arm, limiting how far they can deviate from the reference regardless of prediction quality. The more distal segments, being less structurally constrained, provided the most meaningful test of estimation accuracy.

Distal upper limb segments, particularly the wrists and elbows, were intermittently visible: arm swing displaced them to the image periphery or beyond the field of view, and self occlusion by the torso was frequent.

The accuracy degradation with speed likely reflected three compounding effects: faster locomotion increased limb velocity, raising the probability of motion blur in the rolling-shutter images; arm swing amplitude grew with pace, further reducing

consistent wrist and elbow visibility; and any residual synchronisation mismatch between the foot camera stream and the OpenCap reference data became more consequential at higher speeds, where joints traversed larger distances per frame, and a fixed temporal offset corresponded to a larger positional discrepancy.

The lower limb catastrophic failure rate was also activity speed dependent (**15.8%** overall, rising from **12.0%** at walking to **28.3%** at fast running). These failures are mainly resulting from environments and participant characteristics not well represented in the training data. As an example, occasionally the visual encoder mistook background structures for body keypoints, placing heatmap activations on the scene rather than on the participant. This failure mode is inherently data-driven, and its frequency is expected to decrease as training environment diversity increases, and it will require continued data collection and model development before it can be considered addressed.

The system is therefore more suited to applications that aggregate measurements over time, such as averaged gait profiles, longitudinal monitoring of movement quality, or population-level kinematic comparisons, where isolated catastrophic frames are diluted across many cycles and the underlying biomechanical signal remains recoverable from the majority of correctly reconstructed frames.

A. Keypoint Accuracy Relative to Prior Work

The systems compared here produced equivalent output types but used fundamentally different sensing strategies, evaluated on different activity sets: EgoPoseFormer [19], [20] used head-mounted stereo cameras evaluated on indoor synthetic or real datasets; OpenCap [10] used multiple fixed external cameras requiring a prepared capture volume; and Xsens MVN [21], [22] used a full body IMU suit. Because the systems also differ in evaluation dataset and ground truth definition, Table III is intended as order-of-magnitude context rather than an accurate benchmark.

EgoPoseFormer [19] reports PA-MPJPE of 32.7 mm on the UnrealEgo synthetic indoor dataset and 74.3 mm on the SceneEgo real-world indoor dataset. EgoPoseFormer v2 [20] improves to 22.5 mm on Ego4View-Syn. Our overall PA-MPJPE of 41.5 mm sits between these two results. The comparison is not controlled: both EgoPoseFormer variants use head-mounted stereo cameras evaluated on indoor or synthetic datasets against marker mocap ground truth, while our system uses foot-mounted cameras outdoors with OpenCap-derived references. The camera placement, from downward looking head camera to upward looking foot camera, produces fundamentally different body-segment visibility profiles, therefore the reported PA-MPJPE values are not interchangeable.

Xsens MVN validation during level walking [21] shows hip and knee flexion RMSE in the 3–5° range. Under more dynamic conditions, such as loaded carries, military-specific movements, Mavor et al. [22] report hip flexion RMSE of approximately 4–10° and knee flexion 5–12° depending on task. Our hip RMSE (8.5°) and knee RMSE (8.1°) exceeded

Fig. 6: OpenCap capture setup. Three smartphones are positioned aligned with and at approximately 35° to the walking corridor. Participants always faced the camera array, moving forward and backward along a 4 m corridor while maintaining a face-on orientation throughout.

TABLE III: Comparison of whole-body pose and joint angle estimation methods. Joint angles are flexion/extension RMSE ($^\circ$). Dashes indicate metrics not reported for the corresponding system or setting.

Method	Sensor	Calib.	Setting	PA-MPJPE (mm)	Hip ($^\circ$)	Knee ($^\circ$)	Ankle ($^\circ$)
This work	2 foot cameras	No	Outdoor walk/run	41.5	8.5	8.1	10.4
<i>Egocentric video (head-mounted)</i>							
EgoPoseFormer [19]	Head stereo cameras	No	Indoor synthetic	32.7 ^a / 74.3 ^b	—	—	—
EgoPoseFormer v2 [20]	Head stereo cameras	No	Indoor AR/VR	22.5 ^c	—	—	—
<i>Markerless video (fixed external cameras)</i>							
OpenCap [10]	2 or more smartphones	Yes	Lab/outdoor	$\approx 32^d$	$\approx 4.5^d$	$\approx 4.5^d$	$\approx 4.5^d$
<i>Inertial (wearable IMU suit)</i>							
Xsens MVN [21]	17 IMUs, full body	Yes	Level walking	—	$\approx 3-5$	$\approx 3-5$	$\approx 3-5$
Xsens MVN [22]	17 IMUs, full body	Yes	Dynamic tasks	—	$\approx 4-10$	$\approx 5-12$	$\approx 4-10$

^aUnrealEgo synthetic dataset. ^bSceneEgo real-world dataset. ^cEgo4View-Syn synthetic dataset.

^dReports joint position MAE vs. marker mocap; not equivalent to PA-MPJPE. ^eMean absolute error from OpenCap validation [10], [23].

the best Xsens walking results and were comparable to the higher end of Xsens dynamic task performance.

OpenCap [10] reports joint kinematic mean absolute error of approximately 4.5° and joint position error of approximately 32 mm relative to marker mocap in controlled lab conditions; validation on functional movement tasks confirms similar margins [23]. Our joint angle errors were larger than these values. Critically, OpenCap is also our reference data rather than an independent comparator: the ≈ 32 mm position uncertainty of OpenCap relative to marker mocap sets a practical floor on the PA-MPJPE we can demonstrate against this reference.

Our shoulder flexion RMSE (10.3°) fell within the range reported for Xsens during dynamic tasks, but elbow RMSE (14.8°) was substantially higher than typical IMU or markerless estimates for the same joint. This outlier is consistent with the structural limitation of the foot mounted viewpoint: the elbow and wrist were frequently at the periphery or outside the camera

field of view, and arm swing motion during walking produced inconsistent keypoint visibility that other sensor modalities did not share.

B. Primary failure modes

Visual inspection of high-error frames pointed to several consistent causes. Self-occlusion during arm swing left wrist and elbow keypoints having an obstructed visual signal, degrading upper-limb predictions. At high movement velocities, motion blur and foot impact on ground contact degraded keypoint detection accuracy across the image, reducing heatmap confidence for those joints. In some frames the visual encoder anchored keypoints to background features, rather than to the participant. These background interference cases arose when the recording environment differed substantially from the training distribution; however, their incidence rate significantly reduces as we introduce more relevant and varied data to the training set.

Fig. 7: Overall PA-MPJPE (mean across all 18 joints, L/R averaged) per activity. The connecting line highlights the monotonic trend.

C. Motivation for foot-mounted cameras

Cameras are placed at the foot rather than at alternative body locations for three main reasons. A head or helmet mounted camera aimed downward suffers severe self-occlusion of the lower limbs: the torso and arms block the legs throughout most of the gait cycle, making reliable pose estimation of the lower limbs difficult. Adding further camera views or inertial sensors would increase participant burden and system complexity, contrary to the design goal of minimal instrumentation with only two shoe units and no additional body-worn hardware. A pelvis-mounted camera or IMU could capture trunk movements, but would miss direct ground-contact events. The foot is the only segment that produces unambiguous impact signal at every step, so foot mounting simultaneously captures limb kinematics and the real impact dynamics of locomotion within a single sensor location.

D. Motivation for main metrics selection

Pose accuracy was reported using PA-MPJPE, which removes global rigid-body rotation and uniform scaling before computing the error. This choice reflects the intended use of the system: the output of the neural network is passed to an IK solver that recovers joint angles from the predicted keypoint skeleton. Joint angles are invariant to global translation and rotation, therefore systematic offsets in the global pose of the predicted skeleton do not propagate into the joint angle outputs.

Global body orientation is important for several applications such as those involving joint moments and muscle analysis. The shoe units include an IMU whose recordings were captured synchronously with the camera frames. Fusing IMU-derived heading with the foot-camera keypoint stream is a planned next

step that would recover global orientation estimates without requiring external information.

E. Calibration-Free Operation

IMU suits require up to 17 sensors to be placed, strapped, and verified before each session, followed by a calibration procedure that typically takes another 2–5 minutes during which the participant must hold specific postures to align the sensor reference frames [4], [5]. This setup burden introduces errors whenever sensor placement deviates significantly from its intended position, and operator to operator variability in strap tightness or pad location are known sources of inter-session inconsistency [24]. The proposed system required no such calibration sequence: the network learned the relationship between sensor and body geometry implicitly during training, so users could clip the shoe units on and begin recording immediately. Placement variability was limited to how consistently the sensor sat within the shoe, which depended largely on shoe fit and was otherwise small. Removing both the sensor placement and calibration requirements lowers the operational skill threshold significantly, enabling deployment by non-expert users, a prerequisite for large-scale field studies and unsupervised health monitoring.

F. Limitations

Several limitations of the current system require explicit discussion. As with any camera-based approach, performance degraded under adverse conditions: rapid motion blur, and scene clutter reduced keypoint detection reliability. Furthermore, low ambient illumination is a known but unverified shortcoming. Depth ambiguity was substantially less severe than in fixed external camera systems due to the close proximity of the sensor to the subject, but was not eliminated entirely.

Self-occlusion of body segments by other body parts remained a fundamental constraint of the egocentric viewpoint. Certain joint configurations temporarily removed key anatomical landmarks from view, limiting the network’s ability to reconstruct joint angles at those instants.

Foot-strike shock is a challenge in foot-mounted systems. Because the camera was semi-rigidly attached to the shoe, each heel-strike results in high frequency vibrations to the camera, producing brief but high-amplitude displacements that appeared as motion blur. The rolling-shutter readout architecture of the sensor compounded this effect: because rows are exposed sequentially rather than simultaneously, rapid camera displacement during heel-strike introduced skew across the frame that a global-shutter sensor would not produce.

Upper-body accuracy was noticeably lower than lower-body accuracy, with PA-MPJPE values ranging from 32.6 to 74.8 mm for the shoulder, elbow, and wrist joints. These errors are tolerable for activity recognition and coarse motion classification, but they might be insufficient for the clinical assessment of upper-extremity function. The foot-mounted viewpoint is geometrically well-suited to the lower limbs and inherently less informative about the upper body, so this gap is expected to narrow only modestly with additional training data

Fig. 8: Per-joint PA-MPJPE (L/R averaged) broken down by activity. Each panel shows one activity; joints are grouped into lower limb (blue, MTP1–Pelvis) and upper limb (amber, Shoulder–Wrist). Box: IQR; center line: median; whiskers: $1.5 \times$ IQR; percentages above each whisker indicate the fraction of frames beyond the IQR range.

alone; complementary sensing or a second camera position would likely be necessary.

The current model was trained and validated on walking and running. Extending the activity set to other activities will require paired foot-camera and reference pose data for each new activity class. The egocentric viewpoint and the foot-level perspective differ substantially from activity to activity, making transfer from existing datasets limited. More varied training data is also needed to address several observed failure modes: clothing that obscures limb boundaries, non-standard footwear, complex scene backgrounds, and extreme participant dimensions all corresponded to reduced keypoint detection

reliability in the current model. However, this constraint is inherent to any novel sensor configuration, and the current methodology provides a direct path to address it.

Accuracy figures were reported relative to OpenCap-derived reference poses rather than marker-based optical motion capture. OpenCap itself carries a reconstruction uncertainty of approximately 20–30 mm, so the reported PA-MPJPE values represent error relative to an imperfect reference. True absolute accuracy against a marker-based gold standard remains to be established.

Finally, although the system operates without spatial constraints, training data were collected in a limited set of

Fig. 9: Joint angle waveforms over one normalised gait cycle for seven joints during **fast running** for one participant. Solid lines: mean; shaded areas: ± 1 SD across gait cycles. Blue: OpenCap reference. Dashed orange: system prediction. Gait cycles segmented using the Zeni method [18].

Fig. 10: Qualitative pose reconstruction results for three representative frames. Left to right: third-person view of the participant; left and right foot-mounted camera images with predicted joint heatmap overlays; 3-D keypoint overlay comparing system prediction (green) with OpenCap reference (orange).

environments and activity conditions. The claim that the system generalises to fully unconstrained, in-the-wild conditions therefore cannot be validated with the current dataset. Domain gap between the structured training distribution and arbitrary real-world scenes is an open question, and validation across diverse outdoor environments, populations, and activity modes is required.

G. Future Work

The more immediate priority is consolidating performance on walking and running by increasing variability in the training set: broader coverage of environments, lighting conditions, clothing, footwear, and participant characteristics would reduce the failure modes observed at the current dataset scale. Furthermore, increasing joint angle accuracy beyond the current results is a near-term target. One candidate approach is pose refinement optimisation, which iteratively refines the IK solution by minimising keypoint reprojection error under biomechanical constraints; applied to a monocular markerless system, it reduced lower-limb errors from the $6\text{-}11^\circ$ range to approximately 5° [25] with no additional sensor hardware or retraining. Extension to other activities follows naturally once this foundation is robust, but each new activity class will require dedicated paired data collection.

Additional validation against optical motion capture is needed to characterise absolute accuracy independently of OpenCap’s own reconstruction error. Such a comparison would also allow the system to be benchmarked against existing wearable and video-based methods on a common reference standard, and would support deployment in clinical and patient populations where accuracy requirements are more stringent.

Each shoe unit already records 6-axis inertial data synchronously with the camera frames; connecting this stream to the inference pipeline would provide explicit foot-contact timing and resolve the global orientation ambiguity.

A promising direction for accuracy improvement is replacement or augmentation of the inverse-kinematics stage with a biomechanically-informed model. Differentiable biomechanics pipelines that enforce anatomical joint constraints during pose optimisation have recently been shown to reduce physically implausible estimates and improve joint angle accuracy [26]. Integrating such a model downstream of the keypoint network would leverage the foot-mounted camera’s viewpoint advantage while correcting the residual errors that arise from projective ambiguity and self-occlusion.

Finally, reducing end-to-end inference latency to enable real-time feedback would open applications in sports coaching, rehabilitation, and consumer wearables where on-the-fly analysis is a prerequisite.

VII. CONCLUSION

Collecting large scale biomechanical motion data in natural environment remains a persistent barrier in gait analysis and human movement science. Existing solutions either confine participants to instrumented capture volumes or require complex multi-sensor setups with lengthy calibration.

We presented a system that addresses this constraint through two wide-angle cameras mounted on the laces of ordinary shoes. A machine learning-based architecture reconstructed full-body skeletal pose directly from the dual foot-camera streams without any calibration. Evaluated on 23 participants during outdoor walking and running against OpenCap-derived reference data, the system achieved an overall PA-MPJPE of 41.5 mm, with hip and knee flexion RMSE of 8.5° and 8.1° respectively.

The primary contribution is a practical reduction in deployment barrier. Compared with conventional IMU suits, the system eliminated the up to 17-sensor placement and per-session calibration procedure, required no specialist operator, and imposed less than 35 g of additional mass per shoe. Compared with fixed-camera markerless systems, it imposed no restriction on recording location. These properties, taken together, make repeated, long-duration, and natural movement data collection feasible at a scale that current motion capture systems cannot match (Figure 1).

The most immediate next steps are IMU integration to recover global orientation and foot-contact timing, and expansion of the training dataset to consolidate performance across more diverse real-world conditions. Validation against optical motion capture as a gold-standard reference will also be required.

Foot-mounted egocentric cameras offer a route to continuous, calibration-free biomechanical monitoring, bringing motion capture out of constrained environments and into everyday life.

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APPENDIX

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL

Joint angle waveforms for the remaining three locomotion conditions are shown in figures [Figures 11–13](#).

Fig. 11: Joint angle waveforms over one normalised gait cycle for seven joints during **walking**. Solid lines: mean; shaded areas: ± 1 SD across gait cycles. Blue: OpenCap reference. Dashed orange: system prediction. Gait cycles segmented using the Zeni method [18].

Fig. 12: Joint angle waveforms over one normalised gait cycle for seven joints during **brisk walking**. Solid lines: mean; shaded areas: ± 1 SD across gait cycles. Blue: OpenCap reference. Dashed orange: system prediction. Gait cycles segmented using the Zeni method [18].

Fig. 13: Joint angle waveforms over one normalised gait cycle for seven joints during **slow running**. Solid lines: mean; shaded areas: ± 1 SD across gait cycles. Blue: OpenCap reference. Dashed orange: system prediction. Gait cycles segmented using the Zeni method [18].